

KNOW-HOW TRANSFER IN AN ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEM

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Conference Key Areas: *Entrepreneurship Education, Mentorship and Tutorship*

Keywords: *entrepreneurial ecosystem, know-how, university entrepreneurship, startups, entrepreneurship training*

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ABSTRACT

Universities have a very important role in entrepreneurial education. University students are not only trained in their specific areas, but they are also trained in entrepreneurial skills to lead teams and to develop leading innovations that will be applied into different markets.

Since 2012, the entrepreneurial ecosystem from Polytechnic University of Valencia (Spain), StartUPV, has implemented several education programs for its community, creating a whole learning roadmap with specific training for each stage of the startup. For instance: hypothesis validation, sales funnel, finance, etc. However, one of the main challenges was how to transfer the know-how generated by each startup to the entire ecosystem.

Beyond mentoring some projects altruistically, the need was detected to create a framework in which the entrepreneurs themselves could share their knowledge with the rest of their colleagues in the ecosystem. To this end, StartUPV Academies were created in 2015.

These sessions consist of small training pills, led by a member of one of the startups in the ecosystem, on a variety of topics: a new programming language, tips for creating marketing campaigns on social networks, how to negotiate with investors, etc.

More than 200 entrepreneurs have attended the StartUPV Academies, and an average of 8 sessions have been held per year. In this paper we analyze these programs, including the main conclusions of more than 5 years of implementation.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the objectives of the UPV is to train its students in entrepreneurial skills at all levels. Specifically, for those projects that access the StartUPV incubator program, an itinerary has been created according to the degree of maturity of the company and the phase of the program in which it is located.

Throughout this itinerary, they receive training on business model generation[1], sales strategy, finances for entrepreneurs[2], business strategy[3], etc.

Moreover, to complement this training provided by the university, entrepreneurs have developed considerable expertise to share with the rest of their peers. This knowledge, enriched by their own entrepreneurial experience, is of enormous value for the growth of the ecosystem.

In this paper, we will present the main initiatives that have been launched in the StartUPV ecosystem to transfer this knowledge among the entrepreneurs who are part of it.

2 TRANSFERRING KNOWLEDGE IN AN ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEM

Through the StartUPV program, an entrepreneurial value chain is created where the entrepreneurs themselves nurture each other, enriching the ecosystem as a consequence. In addition, StartUPV entrepreneurs are a reference for all students of

the university, serving as an example through the experience gained in the adventure of undertaking business projects.

As part of this entrepreneurial ecosystem, entrepreneurial projects, startups, and companies benefit and take advantage of the institutional support, the services of the UPV, and the whole network of experts of IDEAS UPV.

However, the challenge lies in how to transfer knowledge among entrepreneurs of the ecosystem. For this reason, in 2015, the StartUPV Academies were introduced and, later, in 2016, the mentoring program. With these activities, entrepreneurs contribute other projects with their experience, increasing the value of the ecosystem itself.

2.1 StartUPV Academies – Universal transfer

As the ecosystem grew, the need was detected to find a formula where the entrepreneurs themselves could share their knowledge with the rest of the startups. To this end, StartUPV Academies were created, consisting of short training sessions on a very specific topic of interest to the ecosystem in general.

2.2 Mentoring program – Personalized transfer

The fact that more than 30 startups are housed in the same space means that knowledge is transferred in a natural way. The entrepreneurs themselves generate synergies between them and help each other altruistically.

The problem with this unstructured mentoring is that it does not reach all the teams equally, and the involvement of the parties is not equal. For this reason, StartUPV launched the mentoring program in 2016, in which we match senior entrepreneurs who act as mentors with junior entrepreneurs.

3 RESULTS

3.1 StartUPV Academies

Since 2015, a total of 37 StartUPV Academies have been held on the following topics:

Table 1. StartUPV Academies topics

Branding	Guerrilla LinkedIn; Leadership; How to create a community of FANS of your brand on Twitter.
Marketing & Communication	Growth Hacking; Inbound Marketing; Introduction to SEO; 2-sided user acquisition; Social Media Marketing; Marketing Automation and CRM; Sales Funnel Canvas; Media Relations and Press Releases; SEO for startups: tips to improve your online presence; HubSpot: How to boost your startup using the most powerful digital marketing tool on the market.
Investment & Funding	Crowdfunding; Capital increases: Finances for entrepreneurs; TechTransfer; Tips for applying for the Fundación Repsol Entrepreneurs Fund; Investment Tips.

Product	Machine design and product approval; Product development; Introduction to Meteor.
Legal & Talent	Data Protection Compliance; Legal mechanisms to attract and retain talent. Legal and tax implications; How to attract talent at the UPV; Choose a successful team; Phantom Shares; Attracting qualified personnel; How to interview in selection processes; Legal doubts against COVID-19; How to make customers pay; Structure of a contract. Essential clauses.
Misc.	Stress management; Bitcoins for dummies; Business model for accelerated development of patentable technologies.

3.2 Mentoring program

Since 2016, a total of 104 pairs of senior entrepreneurs with junior entrepreneurs have been created. From 2018 to 2021, a total of 542.5 mentoring hours have been held in 309 meetings.

4 SUMMARY

Knowledge transfer in an entrepreneurial ecosystem takes place naturally by the very nature of the space and the people who form it. In recent years, the StartUPV ecosystem has detected the need to structure this knowledge transfer in specific activities in order to reach more beneficiaries and maintain a medium-long term commitment.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is partially supported by The Innovative Entrepreneur Campus Program, coordinated by the Subdirector General of Entrepreneurship, Cooperativism and Social Economy of the Generalitat Valenciana.

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